

Management of status epilepticus in adults: PROTOCOL for a systematic review of clinical practice guidelines

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) is defined as “a condition resulting either from the failure of the mechanisms responsible for seizure termination or from the initiation of mechanisms, which lead to abnormally, prolonged seizures (after time point t1). It is a condition, which can have long-term consequences (after time point t2), including neuronal death, neuronal injury, and alteration of neuronal networks, depending on the type and duration of seizures” (Trinka et al., 2015). SE is a neurological emergency affected by significant neurologic deficits (Legriell et al., 2010) and high mortality (Neligan et al., 2019). Mortality in adults is around 16%, with high variability (2% to 39%) that could be only partially explained by a different distribution of known prognostic variables (mainly aetiology) and methodological heterogeneity among studies (Neligan et al., 2019). Other unknown factors are likely involved and it is particularly interesting that mortality appears to be stable across decades (Neligan et al., 2019). This stability could be partly explained by two opposing trends, namely the progressive ageing of susceptible patients on the one hand, and the improved management of acute neurologic conditions - including the expansion of anti-seizure medications (ASMs) available for SE (Amengual-Gual et al., 2019) - on the other hand. An additional factor could be the gap between management based on clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) and actual clinical practice. This gap has been shown to impact patient outcomes and appears to be stable over decades (Cascino et al., 2001, Kellinghaus et al., 2019, Sairanen et al., 2021, Scholtes et al., 1994, Uppal et al., 2018, Vignatelli et al., 2008).

CPGs are “statements that include recommendations, intended to optimize patient care, that are informed by a systematic review of evidence and an assessment of the benefits and harms of alternative care options”(Medicine, 2011). The expected benefits of CPGs are influenced by many factors, including their methodological quality, organizational issues, and physicians and patients factors (Grol et al., 1998, Woolf et al., 1999). Another crucial issue is the applicability of the CPGs (Brouwers et al., 2010b), that is, providing CGP users with tools for the clinical implementation, such as an analysis of facilitators and barriers,

resource considerations, monitoring or audit criteria, and instructions, summary documents, checklists, algorithms. All of these are key factors that influence CPG acceptance, adherence, and the confidence of end-users. Among the other domains of CPG quality (scope and purpose, stakeholder involvement, rigour of development, clarity and presentation, editorial independence), applicability is one of the most neglected and low-scoring domains (Alonso-Coello et al., 2010, Knai et al., 2012), and this limitation has not changed over the past two decades (Gagliardi and Brouwers, 2015). CPGs for the management of SE have been available for many years, yet several studies have reported that clinicians often do not follow recommendations (Uppal et al., 2018). Common deviations from CPGs include delayed administration of anticonvulsants and overuse of benzodiazepine (Uppal et al., 2018).

In the Emilia-Romagna region, northern Italy, several epidemiological and prognostic studies on SE have been performed for two decades (Vignatelli et al., 2003, Vignatelli et al., 2005, Govoni et al., 2008, Giovannini et al., 2015, Giovannini et al., 2017, Giovannini et al., 2019, Orlandi et al., 2020, Mutti et al., 2022), and through this time frame the 30-day case-fatality has shown and still shows high peaks: 39% in Bologna in 1999-2000 (Vignatelli et al., 2003), 31.5% in Modena in 2013-2015 (Giovannini et al., 2017), 50% in Parma in 2015 (Mutti et al., 2022). About 20 years ago, in Emilia-Romagna, a study found that patients with inadequate drug treatment had a worse 30-day case-fatality (Vignatelli et al., 2008). The commonest mistakes observed were administration of a lower than recommended dose of any type of drug and reiterated use of benzodiazepines after the first two levels of intervention. It was hypothesised that the lack of implementation of a formal treatment protocol for SE was a possible explanatory factor.

Also because of these premises, a multicenter prognostic study on SE was devised and launched, including all the neurological and intensive care units of Emilia-Romagna, with funding from the Italian Ministry of Health (S**T**atus **E**Pile**P**ticus in **ER** – **S**TEPPER – bando 2016 Ricerca finalizzata ordinaria RF-2016-02361365). One of the aims of the study is to identify, provide and disseminate recommendations for the optimal management of SE, and to provide validated quality indicators to be implemented in clinical practice. Specifically, a 3-step audit process will be performed, the first of which will be the definition of a diagnostic-therapeutic pathway for SE - including quality indicators of management – based on good quality CPGs, identified through a systematic review. The aims of this systematic review will be to 1) appraise the quality of CPGs, assuming that the Applicability domain may be particularly overlooked; 2) outline commonalities and discrepancies in recommendations; 3) highlight research gaps in the management of SE.

Objective

The purpose of this protocol is to report the rationale and methodology of a systematic review of CPGs on the diagnostic and therapeutic management of SE in adults.

Methods

This protocol is following the methodology suggested by Johnston et al. (Johnston et al., 2019) and is registered with PROSPERO database and published on the Zenodo repository and Researchgate.

Eligibility criteria

The unit of analysis is CPG that include recommendations on the diagnostic and therapeutic management of SE in adults. We defined inclusion and exclusion criteria according to the PICAR framework for systematic reviews of CPGs (Table 1)(Johnston et al., 2019). To ensure clinical relevance and minimal quality, eligibility will be limited to CPGs issued by national health authorities, major national or international professional organisations or societies, reporting a methodology of CPG development, published since 2010, without language restrictions. For each guideline, if the case, we will include the latest version. We will not apply

any sex, ethnicity, or setting restrictions. We will exclude guidelines addressing SE in children. The following clinical subgroups will be outlined: SE with prominent motor phenomena (“convulsive” SE - CSE), SE without prominent motor phenomena (“non-convulsive SE” – NCSE), refractory SE (RSE). The interventions of interest will be procedures/tests (blood tests, neuroradiology) for diagnosis of the etiology of SE, procedures/tests (EEG) for diagnosis of seizure condition, any treatment of SE (excluding etiologic treatments). These elements will be framed, if appropriate and possible, by the duration of SE and setting (pre-hospital, hospital).

Data sources and searches

We will search PubMed and EMBASE databases (see Appendix for applied search strategies), guideline registries, EBM databases, point-of-care tools, websites of governmental organisations, websites of international neurologic societies (see list in Appendix). Finally, we will search Google for additional unique records using broader search terms for “status epilepticus” and “guideline”, sifting through the first 100 results, and scan the reference lists of all retrieved CPGs.

Study selection and data extraction

Two researchers (LV and MC) independently will screen the titles and abstracts of identified records for eligibility. Full text will be retrieved for all records that appear to meet the inclusion criteria and checked for eligibility by two researchers (LV and MC) independently. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion. For all included CPGs we will also retrieve any associated companion article (e.g. methodology supplements and background documents) or relevant accompanying online information. One researcher (LV) will extract document metadata (title, year, country of origin, authors, funding source, CPG development method, quality grading system). Two researchers (LDV, VT) will extract the text of the recommendations of interest. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion.

Quality assessment

Three researchers (LV, MC, SM) will independently assess the quality of the CPG using the AGREE II tool (Brouwers et al., 2010a), which covers 23 items in the domains of scope and purpose, stakeholder involvement, rigour of development, clarity of presentation, applicability and editorial independence. Each item will be scored on a 7-point Likert-type scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). A final quality score for each domain will be calculated, according to the AGREE II user’s manual, and provided on a percentage scale. “High quality” of a CPG will be defined according to the suggestions in the manual as >70% on all domain scores.

Data synthesis and analysis

We will report in a table the main characteristics of the included CPGs. We will present AGREE II scores for each CPG and for each individual domain, then for each domain in total. Based on the scores of the individual domains, we will identify issues that contribute to decreased guideline quality. We will construct a recommendation matrix to assist us in systematically comparing, categorizing, and summarizing the nature of recommendations reported between and within indications. The quality of evidence supporting recommendations will be assessed. To facilitate a direct comparison of the quality of evidence between recommendations reported by different CPGs, the rating systems of all CPGs will be reviewed and compared with each other. Recommendations pertaining to SE’s diagnostic and therapeutic management will be considered, calculating the proportion of CPGs that cover the different types of indications. We will

use thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) to help identify common themes among the recommendations. Each recommendation matrix will be used to facilitate the process. First, we will isolate recommendations and their associated thematic codes to appear side-by-side. Next, one reviewer will read and re-read each recommendation and its associated code to become more familiar with the data. The reviewer will then revisit and refine the codes (if necessary) using an iterative process as new ideas emerge. Once completed, the revised set of codes will be examined and broader themes will be identified. After a final set of thematic codes has been developed, another reviewer will independently review and challenge them. The final set of themes will be agreed upon through consensus.

Table 1. PICAR inclusion criteria (Johnston et al., 2019).

Population, clinical indication and condition(s)	Adults with SE, in any clinical setting (out of hospital; ER; hospital; ICUs) The following clinical conditions will be outlined: CSE, NCSE, RSE
Interventions	Any diagnostic management Any therapeutic management
Comparator(s), comparison(s), and (key) content	All comparators and comparisons are of interest Key contents: the following elements will be outlined: - procedures/tests on diagnosis of etiology (blood tests, neuroradiology) - procedures/test on diagnosis of seizure state (EEG) - treatment of SE (etiologic treatment will be excluded) These elements will be framed, if appropriate and possible, according to age (children vs adults), SE duration, semeiology (CSE, NCSE), setting (pre-hospital, hospital), response to therapy (RSE).
Attributes of eligible CPGs	Publishing body: national health authorities and national or international professional organisations or societies Language: any Year of publication: 2010-present System of rating evidence: Any Scope: Must contain recommendations on diagnosis and / or treatment of SE Recommendations: At least one eligible recommendation reported
Recommendation characteristics	Levels of confidence: No restrictions Locating recommendations: Within CPG text, tables, algorithms or decision paths

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Appendix – Search strategy

PUBMED

Search terms will be as follows:

#	Search
1	"Status Epilepticus"[Mesh]
2	"status epileptic*" OR "epileptic status" OR "Petit Mal Status" OR "Absence Status" OR "epileptic state*"
3	1 OR 2
4	"guideline"[Publication Type] OR "practice guideline"[Publication Type] OR guideline*[title] OR recommendation*[title] OR guidance*[title]
5	3 AND 4
6	5 AND [2010:2022][pdat]

EMBASE

Search terms will be as follows:

#	Search
1	'epileptic state'/exp
2	'status epileptic*':ti,ab,kw OR 'epileptic status':ti,ab,kw OR 'petit mal status':ti,ab,kw OR 'absence status':ti,ab,kw
3	1 OR 2
4	guideline*:ti OR recommendation*:ti OR guidance*:ti
5	3 AND 4
6	5 AND [2010-2022]/py
7	6 AND [embase]/lim NOT (([embase]/lim AND [medline]/lim)

Guideline registries, EBM databases, point-of-care tools

ECRI Guidelines Trust

<https://guidelines.ecri.org/>

International Guidelines Library, Guidelines International Network (GIN)

<https://g-i-n.net/international-guidelines-library/>

NHS Evidence Search

<https://www.evidence.nhs.uk/>

Catalogage et l'Indexation des Sites Médicaux de langue Française (CISMeF)

<https://www.cismef.org/cismef/>

CPG Infobase: Clinical Practice Guidelines

<https://joulecma.ca/cpg/homepage>

Red Española de Agencias de Evaluación de Tecnologías Sanitarias y Prestaciones del Sistema Nacional de Salud

<https://redets.sanidad.gob.es/>

Trip Medical database

<https://www.tripdatabase.com/>

UpToDate

<https://www.uptodate.com/contents/search>

DynaMed

<https://www.dynamed.com/>

Governmental organisations

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence NICE

<https://www.nice.org.uk/>

Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network SIGN

<https://www.sign.ac.uk/>

Haute Autorité de Santé HAS

https://www.has-sante.fr/jcms/c_431294/en/clinical-practice-guidelines-cpg

International neurologic societies

American Academy of Neurology (AAN)

<https://www.aan.com/practice/guidelines>

American epilepsy society (AES)

<https://www.aesnet.org/about/position-statements>

International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE)

<https://www.ilae.org/guidelines>

European Academy of Neurology (EAN)

<https://www.ean.org/research/ean-guidelines/guideline-reference-center>